

GENDER BIAS AGAINST WOMEN ACCESSING HEALTH CARE IN THE UNITED STATES

by

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Abstract

Women in the United States are facing gender bias while seeking access to basic health care. With differences in care existing between men and women, overall health status is also affected. Gender bias is also prevalent between the disparities that exist in the diagnosis and treatment options that are recommended to men and women, even though women are more proactive in the use of preventive care (Kent, 2012). Undergraduate students from California State University, Fullerton were asked to complete a survey about their demographics, external environment, personal health care practices, health status, and access to health care. This project focuses on topics such as gender bias in the health care system, and access to care by race and ethnicity. Strategies to prevent bias in the health care system are mentioned as well. The goal of this project is to test if there is a correlation between the differences in health care between men and women, and gender bias. Chi-square tests were used to analyze the data collected to examine the relationships between multiple variables and gender. The purpose of this study is to bring awareness to these differences in health care, and provide recommendations to reduce gender bias in the healthcare field.

BACKGROUND

In the United States, gender bias is a prominent factor for women that need to access health care. Alspach (2017) suggests that bias against women is present when they are diagnosed or treated, giving them a lower degree of established care than men in comparable health status. Effects of this bias include worsened health outcomes for women, which are marked by higher rates of morbidity and mortality, followed by higher complications as well (Alspach, 2017). Despite the increase in life expectancy in the U.S., disparities in mortality and morbidity intersect between race, ethnicity, and gender (Rapp et al., 2021). Arguments are still used to justify discrimination against gender minorities and women, while upholding the traditional foundations of male privilege (Gupta et. al, 2019). This literature review examines gender bias against women accessing care in the health care system. Additionally, it mentions a few factors that contribute to the disparities women face when accessing health care and how these factors interact with each other.

Gender Bias in the Health Care System

Our current health system reflects both gender inequalities and norms (Gupta et al., 2017). For example, many services provided for women (i.e. maternal or child health) neglect the fact that women are at greater risk for other diseases. Moreover, gender norms are reinforced by clinicians that resist men's engagement in pediatric and maternal care (Gupta et al., 2017). Gender bias is also prevalent between the disparities that exist in the diagnosis and treatment options that are recommended to men and women, even though women are more proactive in the use of preventive care (Kent, 2012). For instance, men are offered more effective procedures (i.e. joint replacement) than women. Consequently, this literature describes that gender bias is still present in multiple aspects of health care although the disparities are identified and known (Kent,

2012). Gender bias can also be specifically tied back to those accessing care in cardiology, surgery, or critical care, with women facing barriers in each (Kent, 2012).

Access to Care

Moreover, evidence shows that out of the 330 million people that inhabit the United States, about 165.5 million women receive substandard health care, making this a barrier in access to care (Alspach, 2017). Consequently, physicians have prescribed women less pain medication as compared to men after abdominal surgery (Alspach, 2017). Some barriers to health care access include the high costs of care, delays in receiving care, or lack of health insurance, all of which are underlying determinants of women's health (Rapp et al., 2021). Additionally, affordability and availability barriers determine the overall health of women. Even when women are insured, they have difficulty paying medical bills, their out-of-pocket costs are higher, and they tend to use more health care services (Rapp et al., 2021). Women are still facing problems with access to care despite being given the same services and resources as men.

Access to Care Differs by Race and Ethnicity

In the study conducted by Rapp et al. (2021), there is a relationship between women's barriers to accessing health care and state-level sexism, which differs by the frequency of needing care, race, and ethnicity. Furthermore, Hispanic and Black women are at a greater risk of experiencing sexism and its health-related impacts than White women due to their position with oppression by both race, ethnicity, and gender (Rapp et al., 2021). Kent (2012) mentions that socioeconomic status or race of a patient influences treatment recommendations. Studies have shown that among nonwhite women, there were very low rates of cardiovascular procedures as

compared to White women (Kent, 2012). Not only does evidence prove that women are having trouble accessing care, but this is due to factors such as race and ethnicity.

STRATEGIES TO PREVENT BIAS IN HEALTH CARE

Multiple approaches have been implemented to reduce and prevent gender bias in health care settings (Alspach, 2017). A starting place is to allow those in health care to gain some insight and awareness of their own vulnerabilities to this type of prejudice in their workplace (Alspach, 2017). Gupta et al. (2017) describes that a type of action to use to shift gender norms and promote gender equality requires focusing on making the workplace more gender equitable, eliminating gender bias in research, and reforming the workplace. Gender bias in health systems can also be prevented by holding systems accountable to the people they serve, giving value to those in health care, and decreasing gender inequality in health care overall (Gupta et al., 2017). By having a better understanding of the causes of gender-based health disparities in the outcomes of health care, we can fashion workable remedies (Kent, 2012). By following and implementing these strategies in the workplace, gender bias can be prevented in health care.

Gender bias has been present in the health care system for many decades now. From Alspach (2017), gender bias is the unequal access of medical treatment that cannot be justified on the basis of an underlying health condition. Reducing gender bias will take more than discussing with health care providers; thus, proper guidelines need to be followed for it to be eradicated. The emphasis on reproductive health and misconceptions about women's health in general are why women have been underrepresented in health care studies (Kent, 2012). Alspach (2017) suggests that more studies and research is needed to help others understand how provider

bias affects care, determine which interventions are effective in preventing gender bias in health care, and how to motivate health care providers to control implicit bias in the workplace.

METHOD

Research Design

The research design used for this study was a cross-sectional study design. This type of study design was used since research was gathered at a single point in time and constraints on time and resources. Additionally, due to these constraints, the sampling design used was convenience sampling. Convenience sampling was chosen to get results from a population that was close at hand. This approach was used through social media platforms, such as Instagram and using Canvas to send out emails to Public Health students. Three professors were emailed to see if they could post the survey as an announcement on their Canvas course page. This helped with receiving over 20 more responses during the time that the survey was open. Regarding confidentiality of data collection and storage, the data was stored in Qualtrics, self-reported, and confidentiality was maintained through anonymity. In addition, the data was only shared between two researchers. The survey had to get approved by the IRB before being able to field it out to CSUF students. SPSS, Version 28 was used to analyze the data from the survey.

For data collection in quantitative methods, a questionnaire was used and designed using the online survey software and insight platform Qualtrics. There were a total of 28 questions, consisting mostly of multiple choice response options. On the survey itself, there are 33 questions in total, but 5 of them are transition questions with no response options. The demographic variables were measured with four questions asking the age, race/ethnicity, gender, and income of each respondent. Additionally, 18 other questions were derived from the 2021 CHIS Adult CAWI Questionnaire, two questions were from SurveySparrow's "Patient

Satisfaction Survey Questions to Ask”, and three questions were self-written by the Primary Investigator. Moreover, one additional question was from the Nevada Commission for Women: Gender Equality Survey. To participate in the study, participants needed to meet the eligibility criteria of being a CSUF undergraduate student and at least 18 years of age. Participation in the survey was completely voluntary and anonymous. Participants were also given two and a half weeks to complete the survey from November 15th, 2022 to December 5th, 2022. Overall, the response rate for the survey was 35.9%. Additionally, sample size was determined by administrative data from California State University, Fullerton (see Figure 1.1, 1.2).

Figure 1.1

Spring 2022 Demographics

	Female		Male		Non-binary		Grand Total	
	Headcount	%	Headcount	%	Headcount	%	Headcount	%
Child & Adol Studies	1,387	27.6%	76	4.6%	*		1,465	21.9%
Counseling	148	2.9%	24	1.5%	*		173	2.6%
Health Science	30	0.6%	13	0.8%			43	0.6%
Human Services	597	11.9%	96	5.8%	*		697	10.4%
Kinesiology	1,005	20.0%	1,018	61.9%			2,023	30.3%
Nursing	474	9.4%	101	6.1%			575	8.6%
Nursing DNP	86	1.7%	44	2.7%	*		131	2.0%
Nursing-Entry Level	170	3.4%	34	2.1%			204	3.1%
Public Health	982	19.5%	223	13.6%	*		1,206	18.0%
Social Work	151	3.0%	15	0.9%			166	2.5%
Total	5,030	100.0%	1,644	100.0%	*		6,683	100.0%
Grand Total	5,030	100.0%	1,644	100.0%	*		6,683	100.0%

Source: Administrative Data from CSUF (*Spring 2022 Demographics Sex*, 2022).

Figure 1.2

Spring 2022 Demographics

	Asian		Black or African American		Hispanic/Latino		Native Hawaiian or Other Pacific ..		Nonresident alien		Two or more races		Unknown		White		Grand Total	
	Headcount	%	Headcount	%	Headcount	%	Headcount	%	Headcount	%	Headcount	%	Headcount	%	Headcount	%	Headcount	%
College of Health and Human Development	Child & Adol Studies	188	12.3%	21	11.8%	908	26.9%	*	66	27.0%	31	13.9%	24	16.6%	224	23.1%	1,465	21.9%
	Counseling	25	1.6%	10	5.6%	62	1.8%		10	4.1%	*	*	*	56	5.8%	173	2.6%	
	Health Science	15	1.0%	*		18	0.5%		*		*	*	*	*		43	0.6%	
	Human Services	51	3.3%	15	8.4%	486	14.4%	*	28	11.5%	14	6.3%	18	12.4%	82	8.4%	697	10.4%
	Kinesiology	523	34.3%	59	33.1%	975	28.8%	*	62	25.4%	91	40.8%	29	20.0%	279	28.7%	2,023	30.3%
	Nursing	155	10.2%	19	10.7%	249	7.4%	*	20	8.2%	12	5.4%	27	18.6%	92	9.5%	575	8.6%
	Nursing DNP	46	3.0%	*		21	0.6%		*		*	*	*	40	4.1%	131	2.0%	
	Nursing-Entry Level	89	5.8%	*		53	1.6%		*		10	4.5%	*	40	4.1%	204	3.1%	
	Public Health	404	26.5%	39	21.9%	530	15.7%	*	45	18.4%	44	19.7%	26	17.9%	116	11.9%	1,206	18.0%
	Social Work	30	2.0%	*		79	2.3%		*		*	*	*	39	4.0%	166	2.5%	
Total	1,526	100.0%	178	100.0%	3,381	100.0%	12	100.0%	244	100.0%	223	100.0%	145	100.0%	971	100.0%	6,683	100.0%
Grand Total	1,526	100.0%	178	100.0%	3,381	100.0%	12	100.0%	244	100.0%	223	100.0%	145	100.0%	971	100.0%	6,683	100.0%

Source: Administrative Data from CSUF (*Spring 2022 Demographics Race and Ethnicity, 2022*).

Procedure

Participants were asked to complete the Qualtrics survey through the social media platform “Instagram”, Canvas course page announcements, and directly on Canvas via email.

CSUF students who agreed to participate in the survey were able to fill it out from the Qualtrics platform.

Participants

There were a total of 90 adults ranging between the ages of 19 and 46 that participated in the study; however only 76 participants completed the survey on Qualtrics in its entirety (see

Figure 1.3). Of the 76 participants, 92% were between the ages of 19 and 29, while the remaining 8% were between the ages of 31 and 42. Approximately 42.1% identified as Hispanic/Latino, 25% were White, 22.4% were South Asian, 13.2% were East Asian, 5.3% were Mixed race, 5.3% were another Other race not listed, 3.9% were Black or African American, 2.6% were American Indian or Alaska Native, 1.3% were Middle Eastern, 1.3% were of European-descent, and 1.3% were Native Hawaiian or Pacific Islander. As for gender identity, 84.2% who took the survey identified as female, 13.2% identified as male, and the remaining 2.6% identified as Other.

Figure 1.3

Source: Student's Own Data

RESULTS

To test both hypothesis 1 and 2, chi-square tests were conducted to examine whether gender bias was present in the external environment of the healthcare system. Additionally, these tests were also conducted to examine whether gender bias was more common for women to experience than men through factors such as the use of health services, societal attitudes towards women, and access to care.

When testing gender and its association with perceived bias in the external environment of the healthcare system, the results demonstrate no statistically significant relationship between individual/environmental factors of health by gender, $p=0.703$ (see Figure 1.4). Next, when testing gender and its association with the experience of gender bias for women through the use of health services, the results demonstrate no statistically significant relationship between routine check-up by gender, $p=0.147$ (see Figure 1.4). Additionally, when testing gender and its association with societal attitudes towards women, the results demonstrate a statistically significant relationship between equal treatment of men and women by gender, $p=0.03$ (see Figure 1.4). Lastly, when testing gender and its association with the experience of gender bias for women through access to care, the results demonstrate a statistically significant relationship between delay in health care by gender, $p=0.084$ (see Figure 1.4).

Figure 1.4

	Female (N = 63)	Male (N = 12)	p-value (**p<0.1)
Individual/Environmental Factors:			0.703
"Moderately important"	3.20%	8.30%	
"Very important"	42.90%	41.70%	
"Extremely important"	54.00%	50%	
Routine Check-Up:			0.147
"One year or less"	67.70%	66.70%	
"2 years"	24.20%	8.30%	
"3 or more years"	8.10%	25.00%	
Equal Treatment of Men and Women:			0.03*
"Yes"	3.20%	16.70%	
"No"	85.70%	41.70%	
"Sometimes"	11.10%	41.70%	
Delay in Health Care:			0.084*
"Yes"	60.30%	33.30%	
"No"	39.70%	66.70%	

Source: Student's Own Data

Discussion

In the present study, the analyses between gender and multiple variables related to health care and other factors were used to find statistically significant relationships for these variables. With the results of the study, new information and perceptions are available from which the study found that specific variables, such as individual/external factors and routine check-up, did not have a statistically significant relationship with gender. The results of the study showed that there was not a statistically significant relationship between individual/environmental factors of health,

and routine check-up by gender ($p=0.703$, $p=0.147$). In regards to individual/environmental factors of health by gender, 54% of women and 50% of men answered that individual and environmental factors are extremely important to a person's health. With routine check-ups by gender, 67.6% of women and 66.7% of men have been to a medical provider for a routine check-up in one year or less.

Additionally, other results of the study showed that there was a statistically significant relationship between equal treatment of men and women, and delay in health care by gender ($p=0.003$, $p=0.084$). Regarding equal treatment of men and women, 85.7% of women and 41.7% of men answered "No" when asked the question "in your opinion, do you feel that men and women are treated equally?" For delays in health care by gender, about 60.3% of women and 33.3% of men answered "Yes" when asked if they have ever had a delay in health care.

With the purpose and goal of this study, one of the demographic variables was asking participants to identify their gender. This allowed for more conclusions to be drawn about understanding the relationships between each variable and gender. Future research is needed on this topic with a larger sample size to determine what specifically needs to be focused on by health care personnel to adjust their biases in the workplace while giving care to patients.

Reflection

The topic of gender bias in healthcare settings is something that I would like to build upon. Considering if I were to continue my research, I would like to distribute the survey out to more university students and/or those in the healthcare field to get a better understanding and clearer conclusion with my results. Additionally, I was surprised by some of the results I received from the survey itself. Although I was initially expecting a lower response rate, I was

expecting a higher number of male responses to be recorded. Also, I was surprised to find out that most of my variables did not have a statistically significant relationship by gender. With more research and a larger sample size, this study could have had more significant results.

Regarding day-to-day tasks, some tasks came easier than others. Some of the tasks I did well at were collecting data, being able to interpret my results, and reaching out to students to take my survey. The tasks that I struggled with included creating histograms in SPSS, doing data analysis in SPSS, and creating charts in excel to display my results. I would like to eventually learn more about how to use SPSS and improve my skills with this software.

While doing this project, I learned many new things about myself. My strengths in completing this project were asking questions to my mentor if I was unsure about data analysis, completing assigned tasks on time, and keeping track of my data and organizing it in folders on my desktop. However, one weakness that I could improve upon is becoming overwhelmed when not being sure on how to complete a task. I saw this in myself while doing data analysis in SPSS and I would like to challenge myself to improve this weakness in navigating future endeavors.

Limitations

Among this study's limitations was the sample size. Given the time frame of the study and content collected, convenience sampling was the best method to use; however, through the various social media platforms and emailing professors to send out the survey, the ideal sample size was still not reached. This may have been due to other factors, such as the length of the survey, only sending the survey to Public Health students, and if students check their email on a regular basis. Additionally, the response rate overall was 35.9% despite being sent out to 236 students via Canvas email. Sample size was also an issue as a total of 14 responses were deleted

due to incomplete or missing data. In future directions for this study, more research participants are needed to allow the results to be generalized for a larger population.

Conclusion

Gender bias in the United States affects a large number of women who are accessing health care for themselves. The variables that were used and analyzed, including individual/environmental factors, routine-check ups, equal treatment of men and women, and delay in health care, allowed for the potential of the study to show some statistically significant results to make conclusions about women accessing health care and gender bias. However, no statistically significant relationships were determined from the results for individual/environmental factors by gender and routine check-up by gender. More research is needed to understand why gender bias against women occurs in the United States and why this is still a pressing problem. With the findings of this research, health care providers and other personnel, along with public health experts and the delivery system of health care, more awareness and guidelines should be considered when delivering health care to patients.

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